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Antimicrobial Susceptibility Patterns of Bacterial Pathogens Isolated from Pediatric Patients in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Pakistan

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR), Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST), Pediatric Patients, Bacterial Pathogens, Gram-Negative Bacteria, Gram-Positive Bacteria, Kirby-Bauer Disc Diffusion, CLSI Guidelines, Urinary Tract Infection (UTI), Septicemia, Escherichia Coli, Klebsiella Spp, Fosfomycin, Linezolid, Empirical Antibiotic Therapy, Antimicrobial Stewardship

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Background: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as a critical and escalating global health challenge that is affecting the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases contributing to noticeable increase in morbidity, mortality and healthcare expenditures. pediatric patients are particularly susceptible due to their underdeveloped immune systems and frequent exposure to empirical therapy. Inappropriate and excessive administration of antibiotics has accelerated the emergence and dissemination of resistant pathogenic strains reducing the available treatment options and increasing the risk of treatment failure.

Objective: This study was conducted to determine the antimicrobial sensitivity patterns of bacterial pathogens isolated from pediatric patients and generate the local evidence based resistance data that can assist clinicians and physicians in selecting appropriate empirical antibiotic therapy and patient outcomes ultimately minimizing antibiotic resistance.

Methodology: This hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted from January to June 2026 at Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS), Islamabad to evaluate the antimicrobial sensitivity profiles of clinical bacterial isolates obtained from children under 12 years of age. The sample size was calculated using (WHO) World Health Organization calculator. The total 385 clinical specimens were processed using standard microbiological techniques and antimicrobial sensitivity testing (AST) was performed by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. Statistical analysis was performed and data was analyzed using independent *t*-test and Chi-square test to determine the significant associations and differences among variables.

Results: Of 385 pediatric clinical specimens analyzed, 215 (55.8%) showed bacterial growth. Females accounted for (55.1%) and males accounted for (44.9%) of culture-positive cases, with a mean age of 4.55 ± 3.70 years. Urinary tract infections were the most common infections (40.2%), followed by septicemia (27.3%) and soft tissue infections (17.1%). *Escherichia coli* (25.6%) was the predominant isolate, followed by *Klebsiella spp.* (17.2%). No significant association was observed between gender and the distribution of Gram-positive (0.14) and Gram-negative (0.52) pathogens. Among Gram-negative pathogens, Fosfomycin showed highest sensitivity against *E. coli* (93.4% $p=0.002$), while Imipenem demonstrated 95.2% sensitivity against *Salmonella typhi* ($p=0.003$). Among Gram-positive isolates, Linezolid exhibited 100% sensitivity against *Enterococcus spp.*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *MRSA*, and (95.8%) sensitivity against *Staphylococcus aureus* while Chloramphenicol demonstrated significant activity against Gram-positive pathogens ($p=0.006$).

Conclusion: Urinary tract infection was the most common bacterial infection among pediatric patients, with *Escherichia coli* as the predominant pathogen. Fosfomycin showed the highest activity against *E. coli*. These findings provide important local antimicrobial susceptibility data to guide empirical antibiotic selection, improve treatment outcomes, and support antimicrobial stewardship efforts in pediatric healthcare setting.

INTRODUCTION:

Antimicrobial resistance is a global health concern that is a challenge to the prevention and treatment of wide range of diseases. When microorganisms change genetically, it causes the drugs we use to treat or prevent infections to become less effective or even completely useless. While this is a natural mechanism, human activities have accelerated it a lot. A major reason behind this acceleration is excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics in medicine, agriculture and other related fields. According to recent estimates antimicrobial resistance (AMR) causes nearly 5 million deaths annually making it one of the leading reasons of mortality worldwide. This really highlights the growing pressure it's putting on our healthcare systems ^[1]. It does not only effects individual patient but also healthcare costs and overall healthcare infrastructure.

The situation is concerning in pediatric patients as infectious diseases are the major cause of death in this age group. According to WHO over 3 million children worldwide died from AMR related infections in 2022, highlighting a critical threat, especially in South-East Asia and Africa. Due to the underdeveloped immune system of children, especially infants and neonates they are highly vulnerable to bacterial infections. Antibiotics are often prescribed and also used as empirical therapy before laboratory confirmation is available. Although, in many clinical settings, prompt treatment with antibiotics is needed, empirical antibiotic therapy is used without proper knowledge of local susceptibility patterns leading to inappropriate prescriptions ^[2]. This challenge is further complicated by the limited availability of pediatric-specific antimicrobial data that restricts clinicians to make evidence-based decision.

Antimicrobial resistance is considerably variable across regions worldwide depending on difference in clinical practices, intake of antibiotics and overall regulatory infrastructure. The spread of AMR in high income and developed countries is controlled to some extent as they maintain structured antimicrobial stewardship programs and surveillance systems. However, in low- and middle-income countries including many areas of South Asia the level of AMR, continues to be disproportionately high because of the lack of adequate infection control procedures and measures, inadequate access to diagnostic facilities, and unregulated sale and use of antibiotics ^[3]. These factors contribute to the rapid emergence and dissemination of resistant pathogens.

Among pediatric patients a wide range of bacterial pathogens pose a high risk of common infections, including urinary tract infections, respiratory infections, blood stream infections and skin infection. The most frequent isolated organisms include *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. With years of study, these organisms have shown multiple resistances towards the groups of antibiotics, greatly reducing the choices to treat. In underdeveloped countries Studies have shown increased resistance rates both among gram-positive and gram-negative in pediatric patients. Gram-negative organisms pose the most severe threat, as they acquire the capability of developing and transferring the resistant genes ^[4].

The definitions of Multidrug-resistant (MDR), Extensively drug-resistant (XDR) and Pan drug-resistant (PDR) organisms have been developed to better understand and categorize the extent of antimicrobial resistance ^[5]. Prevalence of MDR and XDR bacteria in children is another area of growing concern as these strains are resistant to first- and second-line antibiotics and necessitates the use of second-line or last-resort antibiotics, which are less effective more expensive and their toxicity have not been well established.

Socio-economic and healthcare factors are worsening the problem of antimicrobial resistance in developing countries. Lack of access to qualified health personnel results in the common practice of self-medication and the indiscriminate prescription of antibiotics. In addition, the emergence and spread of resistant organisms or strains can also be facilitated by the usage of sub-standard and counterfeit drugs, poor infection control measures and overcrowding of health facilities. Studies on neonatal sepsis in developing countries has revealed that many infections are attributable to pathogens which are resistant to most first-line antibiotics, complicating treatment and increasing the risk of adverse outcome. These findings highlight the urgent need for intervention in such settings ^[6].

At a broader level, international organizations acknowledge AMR as a serious threat and call for coordinated global action. To rationalize the use of antibiotics, reinforce surveillance systems and encourage the research for new antimicrobials, efforts have been made internationally. As the basis for effective intervention strategies, various reports and policy frameworks stress the significance of local resistance profiles ^[7]. In resource-limited settings, gaps in data and implementation remain, particularly where healthcare systems face multiple competing challenges in spite of these initiatives.

In Pakistan antimicrobial resistance has been rising to an alarming situation, mainly due to unrestricted availability of antibiotics without any prescription, lack of awareness in general public and ineffective implementation of regulatory policies. Various studies and surveys in the different regions of the country, have revealed high degree of resistance among clinical isolates, including those obtained from pediatric patients ^[8]. Yet, many of these studies are narrow in scope of hospitals or regions and do not provide a broad and comprehensive picture of the resistance pattern on national level. Published reports for children are very few that it restricts the extent to which they can be applied to pediatric patients and cases. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST) plays a crucial role in managing against AMR. These laboratory tests provide information on whether a particular bacterial isolate is sensitive or resistant to different antibiotics and helps deciding the most appropriate treatment. ASTs should be performed using standardized guidelines, for example, using procedures recommended by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) ^[9]. Accurate susceptibility data not only improve patient outcomes but also contribute to surveillance efforts by identifying trends and changes in resistance over time.

Besides its clinical importance, susceptibility testing is an important aspect of an antimicrobial stewardship program. This program aims to ensure that antibiotics are used optimally, prescribed only when necessary, reduce the risk of emerging resistance and provides valuable data on local resistance trends. The success of these programs depends on the availability of recent and region-specific data which is still insufficient in many healthcare setting ^[10].

A major difficulty in studying antimicrobial resistance is inconsistency and lack of uniformity in study methods and reporting standards. Variation in sample size, patient population, laboratory techniques and criteria used for interpretation often make it difficult to accurately compare results. It highlights the importance of using standardized methods for data collection and analysis ^[11].

Even though research on antimicrobial resistance has increased over years, some important gaps still exist especially in pediatric patients. Much of the available researches are conducted on adult patient population and their findings cannot be directly applied to pediatric cases due to their unique physiological differences, immune mechanisms and trends in infection. Other than that there are very few longitudinal studies to reveal trends in resistance patterns over a period of time. Filling these gaps is important for developing effective strategies to control antimicrobial resistance and improve patient outcome ^[12].

On antimicrobial susceptibility patterns absence of localized data is major challenge for clinicians. Due to the absence of such important data empirical treatment may not align with current trends and can lead to poor treatment choices and patient outcome. This concern is even more critical in children who have high rates of infections, and require timely and effective treatment ^[13]. Therefore, the studies that provide such region- specific data are important and can be used in clinical practice and for developing healthcare policies and treatment guidelines.

This study aims to address the existing gaps by examining the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of clinical isolates obtained from pediatric patients. Using standardized laboratory protocols, this study seeks to provide precise and relevant data on current resistance trends. In doing so the study aims to help identifying most common pathogen causing infections in children and their response to frequently used antibiotics, ultimately supporting evidence-based treatment and decision.

The importance of monitoring antimicrobial susceptibility patterns for choosing effective treatment and to reduce the spread resistant pathogens have been underlined repeatedly in wide range of national and international studies. On a global scale it is considered a serious public health concern as it contributes to

healthcare-associated complications like, prolonged hospitalization, increased treatment costs, and mortality [14]. The regular surveillance of bacterial resistance patterns is also stressed by the international researchers to guide empirical therapy and improve patient outcomes [15]. Similarly, systematic reviews have reported an alarming rise in resistance among gram negative bacteria to commonly used antibiotics thereby limiting therapeutic options and increasing dependence on broad-spectrum antimicrobial agents [16].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and Settings

Type of study

This study was designed as a Cross-sectional study to evaluate the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of clinical isolates obtained from children.

Location of research

The study was conducted at the Microbiology laboratory of the pathology department at Pakistan Institution of Medical Sciences (PIMS), Islamabad. Clinical samples were collected from (IPD) inpatient department of hospital.

Study duration:

The study was conducted over the period of six months after IRB approval from May 2025 to November 2025.

Size calculation:

The sample size of this study was calculated using the World Health Organization (WHO) sample size calculator based on a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and an expected prevalence of 50%. The total sample size was 385.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:	Exclusion Criteria:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Children age < 12 years, visiting to the hospital were selected as the study population.• Children with suspected bacterial infection were included.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Children who were on antibiotic therapy at the time of sample collection were excluded• Patient whose parents and guardian did not allowed consent.

Study Participants:

All study participants which fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled after the informed consents from the parents and guardian. Demographic of patients were recorded using a questionnaire. After enrollment each patient was assign a code to maintain their confidentiality. The patients were registered in the system and provided with the laboratory request slip. After proper identification, patient was guided for the sample collection. For blood sample, aseptically puncture the vein and the required volume was collected into the sterile culture bottle from patients suspected of septicemia. For urine, a sterilized container was given to the patient and guide them how to collect a proper sample from patients suffering from urinary tract infection

(UTI). Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was collected by a professional physician through lumbar puncture under aseptic conditions from the patients caused by meningitis. After that samples were properly labeled and then immediately transported to the microbiology department. Sample testing was performed according to Standard operating procedures (SOPs).

Culture

Each sample was inoculated by plate streak method. For urine, Cystine-lactose electrolyte deficient (CLED) media and for stool Xylose lysine deoxycholate (XLD) media was used and for wound, pus, blood, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), sputum, endotracheal tube tip, nasal swab and central venous pressure (CVP tip) blood agar, chocolate agar, and MacConkey agar was used respectively. After inoculation, plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in incubator. Following Incubation, the culture plates were examined for bacterial growth. Cultural characteristics were noted.

Gram staining:

Colony isolates were determined by using microbiology methods. First, the Gram stain was used to classify the bacteria into either Gram-positive or Gram-negative bacteria according to cell wall composition. Then, the stained slides were viewed under the microscope 100X to determine their morphology (cocci or bacilli).

Biochemical test:

After the Gram stain, other biochemical tests were conducted to confirm the type of bacteria. In case of Gram-negative bacteria, biochemical tests such as oxidase, catalase, indole, citrate, urea and TSI tests were performed. If the bacteria were Gram positive, then catalase and coagulase tests were done to distinguish between Staphylococcus and streptococcus bacteria.

Preparation of Antibiotic susceptibility Testing:

A few very well-isolated colonies were separated and emulsified in a normal saline N/S for bacterial suspension. A turbidity of suspension was equals to 0.5 Mc Farland standard which corresponds to 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing:

Antibiotics susceptibility tests were conducted using the Kirby-Bauer test on Mueller Hinton agar medium according to the standards provided by Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.

A sterile swab was first dipped into the standardized bacterium suspensions and then streaked across the surface of the medium (Mueller Hinton agar) to produce a lawn culture. Antibiotic disks were then laid on the surface of the medium using sterile forceps or disc dispensers.

The cultures were incubated aerobically for 18-24 hours at 35-37°C.

Interpretation of Results:

After incubation, the zones of inhibition were measured around the antibiotic discs in millimeters using a ruler. The results were interpreted as Sensitive (S) and resistant (R) according to CLSI guidelines.

Statistics Analysis:

All collected data were analyzed on SPSS (statistical package for the social system) version 23. Chi square was applied to categorical variables and independent sample T test for numerical variables. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 385 pediatric samples were included in the study, out of which 170(44.2%) showed no growth, while 215 (55.8%) showed microbial growth. Among positive cases, 97(44.9%) were males and 119(55.1%) were females. The mean age of patients was 4.55 ± 3.70 years. A gender wise distribution of participants, representing that Female comprising 55% and male comprising 45% of the study population, as shown in table 01.

Table 01: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristics	Values
Total participants	385
Male, n (%)	175(45%)
Female, n (%)	210(55%)
Age, mean, SD (years)	4.55 ± 3.70
Age range (years)	0-12

Urinary tract infections accounted for 40.2%, septicemia (27.3%), soft tissue infection (17.1%), upper respiratory tract infection (4.8%), meningitis (3.6%), ventilator-associated pneumonia (3.4%). Catheter-related bloodstream infection (2.4%), surgical site infection 0.8%. Whereas pneumonia and lower respiratory tract infection both accounting for 0.2% of the total cases as shown in figure 01.

Figure 01: Distribution of infections

The prevalence of bacterial pathogens showed that *Escherichia coli* accounted for 25.6%, followed by *Klebsiella spp.* (17.2%). *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were equally prevalent, each contributing 11.2% of infections. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi* each accounted for 10.2%, while *Enterobacter* represented 6.5% of the isolates. *Enterococcus spp.* accounted for 4.2%, MRSA for 2.3%, and *Streptococcus pyogenes* was detected in 1.4% of the total isolates as shown in figure 02.

Figure 02: Prevalence of pathogens

Among Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* was detected in 62.5% females and 37.5% males, *Streptococcus pyogenes* 33% females and 66% males, *Enterococcus spp.* 78% females and 22% males, while *MRSA* represented 20% females and 80% males, with a p-value of 0.14 as illustrated in Table 02.

Table 02: Gender wise distribution of gram positive pathogen.

Gram positive bacteria, N (%)	Female	Male	Total	P-value
Staphylococcus Aureus	15(62.5)	9(37.5)	24(100)	0.14
streptococcus pyogenes	1(33)	2(66)	3(100)	
Enterococcus Spp	7(78)	2(22)	9(100)	
MRSA	1(20)	4(80)	5(100)	
Total	24(58)	17(42)	41(100)	

Escherichia coli accounted for 63.6% females and 36.4% males, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 54.5% females and 45.5% males, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 45.8% females and 54.2% males, *Enterobacter* 42.8% females and 57.2% males, *Salmonella typhi* 45.4% females and 55.6% males, while *Klebsiella Spp* represented 56.7% females and 43.3% males, with a p-value of 0.52 as shown in Table 03.

Table 03. Gender wise prevalence of gram-negative pathogen

Gram Negative Bacteria, N (%)	Female	Male	Total	P-value
Pseudomonas Aeruginosa	11(45.8)	13(54.2)	24(100)	0.52
Escherichia coli	35(63.6)	20(36.4)	55(100)	
Klebsiella pneumoniae	12(54.5)	10(45.5)	22(100)	
Enterobacter	6(42.8)	8(57.2)	14(100)	
salmonella typhi	10(45.4)	12(55.6)	22(100)	
klebsiella Spp	21(56.7)	16(43.3)	37(100)	
Total	95(54.5)	79(45.5)	174(100)	

Amikacin demonstrated sensitivity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (87%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (72.8%). Fosfomycin showed sensitivity against *Escherichia coli* (93.4%). Nitrofurantoin is sensitive against *Klebsiella Spp* (85.7). Cotrimoxazole demonstrated 100% sensitivity against *Enterobacter spp*. Imipenem exhibited high sensitivity against *Salmonella Typhi* (95.2%) as shown in table 04.

Table 04: Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of gram-negative pathogens.

Antibiotics	Susceptibility	P. Aeruginosa	E. Coli	K. Pneumoniae	Enterobacter	Klebsiella Spp	S. typhi	P-Value
Amikacin	Resistant	3(13)	10(18.8)	6(27.2)	11(78.5)	24(64.9)	1(100)	0.001
	Sensitive	20(87)	43(81.2)	16(72.8)	3(22.5)	13(35.1)	0(0)	
	Total	23(100)	53(100)	22(100)	14(100)	37(100)	1(100)	
Cefoperazone Sulbactam	Resistant	10(50)	12(92.3)	7(77.8)	10(90.9)	20(83.3)	--	0.021
	Sensitive	10(50)	1(7.7)	2(22.2)	1(9.1)	4(16.7)	--	
	Total	20(100)	13(100)	9(100)	11(100)	24(100)	--	

Levofloxacin	Resistant Sensitive Total	14(60.8) 9(39.2) 23(100)	28(54.9) 23(45.1) 51(100)	12(66.7) 16(33.3) 18(100)	12(92.3) 1(7.7) 13(100)	23(69.7) 8(24.3) 33(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.119
Cefepime	Resistant Sensitive Total	8(53.3) 7(46.7) 15(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	3(60) 2(40) 5(100)	20(95.2) 1(4.8) 21(100)	0.022
Gentamicin	Resistant Sensitive Total	3(50) 3(50) 6(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	0(0) 1(1) 1(1)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	2(66.7) 1(33.3) 3(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.683
Chloramphenicol	Resistant Sensitive Total	--	--	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	--	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	12(63.1) 7(26.9) 19(100)	0.440
Trimethoprim Sulfamethoxazole	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(66.6) 1(33.4) 3(100)	28(71.7) 11(29.3) 39(100)	7(77.7) 2(22.3) 9(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	5(83.3) 1(16.7) 6(100)	11(55) 9(45) 20(100)	0.601
Ceftriazone	Resistant Sensitive Total	3(50) 2(50) 4(100)	30(66.6) 15(33.4) 45(100)	17(77.3) 5(22.7) 22(100)	13(92.8) 1(7.2) 14(100)	31(93.3) 2(6.7) 33(100)	13(59) 9(41) 22(100)	0.014
Fosfomycin	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	3(6.6) 42(93.4) 45(100)	8(100) 0(0) 8(100)	--	2(28.5) 5(71.5) 7(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.002
Amoxicillin. Clavulanic. Acid	Resistant Sensitive Total	4(80) 1(20) 5(100)	40(76.9) 12(23.1) 52(100)	19(100) 0(0) 19(100)	12(100) 0(0) 12(100)	24(88.9) 3(11.1) 27(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.101
Imipenem	Resistant Sensitive Total	12(57.2) 9(42.8) 21(100)	15(27.7) 39(72.3) 54(100)	13(61.9) 8(38.1) 21(100)	12(85.7) 2(14.3) 14(100)	8(22.8) 27(77.2) 35(100)	1(4.8) 20(95.2) 21(100)	0.003

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Piperacillin. Tazobactam	Resistant Sensitive Total	11(55) 9(45) 20(100)	14(30.5) 32(69.5) 46(100)	11(64.7) 6(35.3) 17(100)	12(100) 0(0) 12(100)	18(60) 12(40) 30(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.008
Meropenem	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	--	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	2(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.151
Ampicillin	Resistant Sensitive Total	5(15) 17(85) 20(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	14(73.6) 5(26.4) 19(100)	0.006
Cotrimoxazole	Resistant Sensitive Total	3(66.6) 1(33.4) 4(100)	1(33.3) 2(66.7) 3(100)	3(37.5) 5(62.5) 8(100)	0(0) 5(100) 5(100)	3(100) 0(0) 3(100)	13(65) 7(35) 20(100)	0.020
Cefiderocol	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(33.3) 2(66.7) 3(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	--	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	0.441
Cefotaxime	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(50)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	3(100) 0(0) 3(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.110
Nitrofurantoin	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	5(12.2) 36(87.8) 41(100)	2(28.5) 5(71.5) 7(100)	--	1(14.3) 6(85.7) 7(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	0.026
Ceftazidime	Resistant Sensitive Total	15(71.4) 6(29.6) 21(100)	12(85.7) 2(14.3) 14(100)	11(84.7) 2(15.3) 13(100)	13(92.8) 1(7.2) 14(100)	7(87.5) 1(12.5) 8(100)	--	0.534

The most sensitive antibiotics against Gram-positive bacteria were Linezolid, Chloramphenicol, Penicillin, and Vancomycin. Linezolid demonstrated 100% sensitivity against *Enterococcus spp.* Both linezolid and chloramphenicol showed equal sensitivity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (95.8%). In *Streptococcus*

pyogenes, penicillin, vancomycin, and linezolid exhibited 100% sensitivity. Additionally, linezolid showed 100% sensitivity against *MRSA*.

TABLE 05: Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern of Gram-Positive Bacteria	Antibiotics	susceptibility	Enterococcus Spp	Staph. aureus	Strep. pyogenes	MRSA	P-value
Piperacillin. Tazobactam	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	7(63.6) 4(36.4) 11(100)	--	4(100) 0(0) 4(100)	0.125	
Ampicillin	Resistant Sensitive Total	3(33.3) 6(66.7) 9(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	--	0.528	
Penicillin	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(25) 3(75) 4(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	0(0) 2(100) 2(100)	--	0.513	
Tetracycline	Resistant Sensitive Total	4(80) 1(20) 5(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	0.146	
Cefoxitin	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	10(59) 7(41) 17(100)	--	4(100) 0(0) 4(100)	0.169	
Clindamycin	Resistant Sensitive Total	4(66.7) 2(33.3) 6(100)	12(54.5) 10(45.5) 22(100)	3(100) 0(0) 3(100)	3(60) 2(40) 5(100)	0.496	
Vancomycin	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(28.6) 5(71.4) 7(100)	4(23.5) 13(76.5) 17	0(0) 2(100) 2(100)	5(100) 0(0) 5(100)	0.522	
Linezolid	Resistant Sensitive Total	0(0) 7(100) 7(100)	1(4.2) 23(95.8) 24(100)	0(0) 2(100) 2(100)	0(0) 5(100) 5(100)	0.897	
Gentamicin	Resistant Sensitive Total	3(60) 2(40) 5(100)	4(16.7) 20(83.3) 24(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	2(40) 3(60) 5(100)	0.177	
Doxycycline	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	12(52.2) 11((47.8) 23(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	0.207	
Chloramphenicol	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	1(4.2) 23(95.8) 24(100)	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(20) 4(80) 5(100)	0.006	
Trimethoprim. sulfamethoxazole	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	9(81.8) 2(18.2) 11(100)	--	3(75) 1(25) 4(100)	0.845	

Fosfomycin	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(100) 0(0) 1(100)	1(33.3) 2(66.7) 3(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	--	0.687
Ceftriaxone	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(100) 0(0) 2(100)	6(50) 6(50) 12(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	4(100) 0(0) 4(100)	0.202
Amoxicillin. Clavulanic Acid	Resistant Sensitive Total	1(33.3) 2(66.7) 3(100)	9(64.2) 5(35.8) 14(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	3(100) 0(0) 3(100)	0.614
Imipenem	Resistant Sensitive Total	2(66.7) 1(33.3) 3(100)	7(63.6) 4(36.4) 11(100)	1(50) 1(50) 2(100)	4(100) 0(0) 4(100)	0.459

DISCUSSION:

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has become one of the most serious global public health challenges threatening the effective prevention and treatment of bacterial infections. The emergence and spreads of resistant pathogens have been accelerated by the inappropriate use of antibiotics. Resulting in increased morbidity, mortality, prolonged hospitalization and healthcare costs. Predicted patients are particularly vulnerable because of their immature immune systems and frequent exposure to empirical antibiotic therapy. Continuous monitoring of bacterial pathogens and their antimicrobial susceptibility patterns is therefore essential to guide appropriate treatment, support antimicrobial stewardship programs, and reduce the burden of resistant infection among children. Similar concerns regarding the growing impact of AMR in predicted populations have been highlighted by Murray et. ^[17]. Within investigated 385 patient samples showed 55.8% culture positivity rate highlights a Burdens of microbial infections. Female patients constituted (55.1%) while male accounted for (44.9). Comparable findings have been reported by Farrukh et al. ^[18] who documented a considerable prevalence of culture-positive bacterial infections among hospitalized children, emphasizing the significant contribution of bacterial diseases to childhood morbidity.

Urinary tract infection was the most common infection observed in this study. The high prevalence of UTIs among children may be related to poor hygiene, anatomical predisposition, malnutrition and immature immune responses. Similar findings have been reported by Khan et al, ^[19] who identified UTIs as one of the leading causes of bacterial infections among pediatric patients in Islamabad. Septicemia was the second most common infection, highlighting the continued importance of bloodstream infections in hospitalized children. Soft tissue infection, upper respiratory tract infection, meningitis, ventilator associated pneumonia, catheter-related bloodstream infection and surgical site infections were identified less common. These findings are consistent with previous reports showing that bloodstream and other healthcare associated infections were remain major contributor of pediatric morbidity and hospital admissions particularly in resource-limited settings where infectious diseases continue to pose major clinical challenges. These observations have been represented by Folgari L ^[20].

Escherichia coli emerged as the most frequently isolated pathogen in our study. The predominance of *E. coli* may be attributed to its strong association with urinary tract infection. Several virulence factors, including adhesins, fimbriae, and the ability to colonize the urinary tract, enable *Escherichia coli* to establish infection more effectively than many other bacterial species. Similar findings were reported by Flores-Mireles et al. ^[21]. *Klebsiella species*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Enterobacter species*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus species*, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), and *Streptococcus pyogenes* were comparatively less prevalent. The isolation of these pathogens reflects diverse spectrum of bacterial pathogens encountered in pediatric clinical settings and highlights their clinical significance in both community- and hospital-acquired infections. Similar findings have also been

reported by Williams et al., [22] who emphasized the predominance of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* species, and other clinically significant bacterial pathogens among pediatric infections and their increasing contribution to antimicrobial resistance worldwide.

The antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of gram-negative bacteria in the present study demonstrated variable responses to commonly prescribed antibiotic. Fosfomycin exhibited excellent sensitivity against *Escherichia coli*, while Amikacin showed considerable effectiveness against *Escherichia coli*, *klebsiella pneumoniae*, *pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Imipenem was identified as most effective against *salmonella typhi*, whereas nitrofurantoin showed good activity against urinary pathogen, particularly *Escherichia coli* and *klebsiella species*. The high susceptibility observed for these antibiotics may be attributed to their relatively restricted use or potent bactericidal against gram negative organism. Similar findings have been reported by Yousaf et al. [23] who documented high sensitivity uropathogens to fosfomycin and amikacin among pediatric patients. Likewise, Khan FU et al. [24] reported by that carbapenem and aminoglycosides remained among the most effective therapeutic option against gram negative bacterial infection in children.

Linezolid demonstrated the highest antimicrobial activity showing excellent susceptibility against *enterococcus species*, *streptococcus pyogenes*, *methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus* and *staphylococcus aureus*. Vancomycin also retained substantial effectiveness against most gram-positive isolates. The preserved susceptibility of these agents may reflect their targeted clinical use and lower rate of inappropriate prescribing compared with commonly used antibiotics. In contrast, reduced susceptibility was observed for several conventional antimicrobial agents indicating the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance among positive pathogens. Similar observations were reported by Azzouz and Preuss [25], who identified linezolid as a highly effective treatment option against resistant gram-positive infections. Furthermore, the Center for Disease Control and Prevention CDC highlighted the continued effectiveness of linezolid and vancomycin against *MRSA* and other clinically significant gram-positive organism [26].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, urinary tract infection was the most common bacterial infection among pediatric patients, with *Escherichia coli* identified as the predominant causative pathogen. Fosfomycin demonstrated the highest antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, indicating its effectiveness in the treatment of pediatric urinary tract infections. The findings of this study provide valuable insight into local pathogens distribution and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns. These data can assist clinicians in selecting appropriate empirical antibiotics for the patients, improving treatment outcomes and promoting rational antibiotic use. Furthermore, continuous surveillance of resistance trends is essential for supporting antimicrobial stewardship and reducing the burden of resistant infection in children.

REFERENCES

- Murray CJL, Ikuta KS, Sharara F, et al. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *Lancet*. 2022;399(10325):629–655.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02724-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0)
- Dadgostar P. Antimicrobial resistance: implications and costs. *Infect Drug Resist*. 2019;12:3903–3910.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S234610>
- Williams PCM, Isaacs D, Berkley JA. Antimicrobial resistance among children in low- and middle-income countries. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2018;18(2):e33–e44.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(18\)30021-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(18)30021-5)
- Le Doare K, Bielicki J, Heath PT, Sharland M. Systematic review of antibiotic resistance in gram-negative bacteria in children. *J Infect*. 2015;71(3):272–281.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2015.05.012>

- Folgori L, Ellis SJ, Bielicki JA, et al. Tackling antimicrobial resistance in pediatric settings. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2017;23(9):e1–e6.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2017.03.018>
- Bilal H, Khan MN, Rehman T, et al. Antibiotic resistance in Pakistan: a systematic review of the past decade. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2021;21:244.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-05906-1>
- Saeed DK, Farooqi J, Shakoor S, Hasan R. Antimicrobial resistance among GLASS priority pathogens from Pakistan (2006–2018). *BMC Infect Dis.* 2021;21:1231.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06795-0>
- Pokharel S, Shrestha P, Adhikari B. Antimicrobial resistance in low-income countries: burden and challenges. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2019;6:105.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2019.00105>
- Tacconelli E, Carrara E, Savoldi A, et al. Discovery, research, and development of new antibiotics: WHO priority list. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2018;18(3):318–327.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(17\)30753-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(17)30753-3)
- Prestinaci F, Pezzotti P, Pantosti A. Antimicrobial resistance: a global multifaceted phenomenon. *Pathog Glob Health.* 2015;109(7):309–318.
<https://doi.org/10.1179/2047773215Y.00000000030>
- Jorgensen JH, Ferraro MJ. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing: general principles and contemporary practices. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2009;49(11):1749–1755.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/647952>
- Alanis AJ. Resistance to antibiotics: are we in the post-antibiotic era? *Arch Med Res.* 2005;36(6):697–705.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2015.05.012>
- Laxminarayan R, Duse A, Wattal C, et al. Antibiotic resistance—the need for global solutions. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2013;13(12):1057–1098.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(13\)70318-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(13)70318-9)
- Klein EY, Van Boeckel TP, Martinez EM, et al. Global increase and geographic convergence in antibiotic consumption. *PNAS.* 2018;115(15):E3463–E3470.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717295115>
- Holmes AH, Moore LSP, Sundsfjord A, et al. Understanding the mechanisms and drivers of AMR. *Lancet.* 2016;387(10014):176–187.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00473-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00473-0)
- Dyar OJ, Huttner B, Schouten J, Pulcini C. What is antimicrobial stewardship? *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2017;23(11):793–798.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2017.01.018>
- Murray CJL, Ikuta KS, Sharara F, Swetschinski L, Aguilar GR, Gray A, et al. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *Lancet.* 2022;399(10325):629–655.
- Farrukh R, Masood S, Nasir F, Rizvi Q, Shakoor I, Naseer A. Culture and sensitivity patterns of various bacteriological agents among children admitted in pediatric department. *Pak Biomed J.* 2022;5(2):152–155. doi:[10.54393/pbmj.v5i2.307](https://doi.org/10.54393/pbmj.v5i2.307).
- Khan R, Iqbal J, Hussain S, et al. Frequency of urinary tract infection in pediatric patients at PIMS Islamabad. *Ann PIMS.* 2024;20(1):45–50. doi:[10.48036/apims.v20i1.856](https://doi.org/10.48036/apims.v20i1.856).
- Folgori L, Ellis SJ, Bielicki JA, Heath PT, Sharland M, Balasegaram M. Tackling antimicrobial resistance in neonatal sepsis. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2017;5(11):e1066–e1068. doi:[10.1016/S2214-109X\(17\)30362-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(17)30362-5).
- Flores-Mireles AL, Walker JN, Caparon M, Hultgren SJ. Urinary tract infections: epidemiology, mechanisms of infection and treatment options. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2015;13(5):269–284.
[doi:10.1038/nrmicro3432](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro3432).

- Williams PCM, Isaacs D, Berkley JA. Antimicrobial resistance among children in low- and middle-income countries. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2018;18(2):e33–e44. [doi:10.1016/S1473-3099\(18\)30021-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(18)30021-5).
- Yousaf A, Khan M, Ali S, et al. Etiology, sensitivity and resistance pattern of urinary tract infections among children. *Pak J Med Health Sci*. 2022;16(11):3421. [doi:10.53350/pjmhs2216113421](https://doi.org/10.53350/pjmhs2216113421).
- Khan FU, Zahoor M, Khan H, et al. Antibiotic drug resistance pattern of uropathogens in pediatric patients in Pakistan. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2023;12(2):395. [doi:10.3390/antibiotics12020395](https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12020395)
- Azzouz A, Preuss CV. Linezolid. In: *StatPearls [Internet]*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) basics*. Atlanta (GA): CDC; 2025